

The Trajectory Of International Criminal Court In African: Challenges And Prospects

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ABSTRACT

The proponents of ICC holds the view that international laws would now be coupled with bites of enforcement through prosecution of war crimes. To what extent has this been achieved in Africa? No doubt, the Africa union resistance and failure to cooperate with UN Security Council referral to ICC in the case of Darfur, and Sudan exposed the selectivity of the enforcement of international criminal law in Africa by ICC. Although, impunity is no longer a shield for atrocities and human right violation in Africa as ICC recently, in July 24th, 2025 convicted two anti- balalaika militia leaders on 28th war crimes and crimes against humanity committed in Central African Republic. However, the pursuit of international criminal justice in Africa through the ICC platform has not been without hitches. Again, the rift between the Africa union as a continental body and the ICC, owing to the AU perception of ICC pursuing selective Justice, and some state parties in Africa refused or failed to comply with the obligation to cooperate with ICC under the Rome statute. No Doubt, has created tensions and aggravated conflicts in some state in Africa. This paper therefore intend to x - ray the trajectory of international criminal court in Africa, with a view of proffering meaningful and achievable practical answers to identified challenges, and placing African in its global strategic space in the fight against war crimes and crimes against humanity.

Keywords: International Criminal Court, war crimes

1. INTRODUCTION

After the Second World War, the Nazi leaders who were alleged to be responsible for the destruction of human lives and dignity were put on trial with the hope that the world would not experience such violence again.

However, in the following years, the spate of violence kept on increasing with no established, permanent global mechanism for the prevention and punishment of such crimes. As a result of this, the agitation for the creation of an International Court to try war crimes and sundry offences increased.

Proponents of the international criminal court (ICC) argued that a permanent court would move the enforcement of human rights to a new level of effectiveness since the bark of the international laws would now be coupled with the bite of enforcement through prosecution.

Following the Second World War, the allied powers established two ad hoc tribunals to prosecute leaders who perpetrated war crimes. The International Military Tribunal for the Far East in Tokyo prosecuted Japanese leaders. In 1948, the United Nations General Assembly first recognized the need for a permanent international court to deal with atrocities perpetrated after the Second World War. At the request of the General Assembly, the International Law Commission (ILC) drafted two statutes by the early 1950s, but these were shelved during the Cold War, which made the establishment of an international criminal court politically unrealistic.

In June 1989, Prime Minister of Trinidad and Tobago, A.N.R Robinson revived the idea of permanent international court by opposing the illegal drug trade. Following Trinidad and Tobago's proposal, the General Assembly tasked the ILC with once again drafting a statute for a permanent court. Whole work

began on the draft, the United Nations Security Council established two ad hoc tribunals in the early 1990s. The International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia was created in 1993 in response to large scale atrocities committed by armed forces during the Yugoslav wars and the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda was created in 1994 following the Rwandan Genocide. The creation of these tribunals further highlighted the need for a permanent international criminal court.

In 1948, the ILC presented its final draft statute for the International Criminal Court to the General Assembly and recommended that a conference be convened to negotiate a treaty that would serve as the court's statute. Therefore, to consider major substantive

issues in the draft statute, the General Assembly, following the adoption of the 1948 United Nations (UN) Convention on the Crime of Genocide (Genocide Convention),¹ invited the International Law Commission (ILC) to study the desirability and possibility of establishing an international judicial organ for the trial of persons charged with genocide.² The ILC studied this proposal at its 1949 and 1950 sessions and concluded that a court of that nature was desirable.³ Following the conflicts in the shocking reports from the armed conflict in the former Yugoslavia and the establishment of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY), the General Assembly urged the ILC to deliberate on a viable statute as a matter of priority, this culminated in the production of a draft statute in 1994.⁴

In order to consider major substantive issues arising from the draft statute, the General Assembly created an Ad Hoc Committee on the establishment of an international criminal court which met twice in 1995. After the consideration of the Ad Hoc Committee's work, the General Assembly established the Preparatory Committee on the establishment of an International Criminal Court.⁵ The task of the Preparatory Committee unlike its predecessor was to formulate a generally acceptable instrument and not simply to assess the visibility and preliminary concerns regarding such project for eventual submission to a diplomatic conference.

A draft treaty indicating unresolved issues and details was laid before a Conference of Plenipotentiaries for negotiation in July 1998 in Rome, where after extremely intense negotiations and compromises on all sides, the International Criminal Court (ICC) statute was signed on 17 July, 1998.⁶ One hundred and twenty states voted in favour of the treaty, seven voted against (US, China, Libya, Iraq, Israel, Qatar, Yemen) and 21 abstained. Following the Rome Conference in the summer of 1998, the US proclaimed that it would not sign the statute.

After the initial proclamation that it would isolate itself from the proceedings of the ICC preparatory commission and create a bad international image⁷ though the US had earlier signed the draft statute, it withdrew the signature on 6 May, 2002, making it clear that it had no intention of ratifying the instrument. This connoted that US was no longer bound to respect the object and purpose of the treaty. However the ICC statute finally entered into force on 1st July 2002.

1.2. Organs of the Court

The International Criminal Court has four organs: the Presidency, the Judicial Division, the Office of the Prosecutor and the Registry.

a. Presidency

The Presidency is responsible for the proper administration of the Court (apart from the office of the prosecutor). It comprises the President and the First and Second Vice-Presidents, three judges of the Court who are elected to the Presidency by their fellow judges for a maximum of two-to-three-year terms⁸.

b. Judicial Divisions

¹ General Assembly Resolution 260 (1) (9) December 1948

² This 1948 convention on the prevention and punishment of the crime of Genocide Art VI, 78

³ ILC on the work of its second session (5 June – 29 June, 1960).

⁴ Crawford J. 'The ILC Adopts a Statute for an International Criminal Court' 89 AJIL (1995) P 404

⁵ General Assembly Resolution 50/46 (11 December, 1995)

⁶ 37 ILM (1998), 999

⁷ Sheffer David J.; *Staying the Course with the International Criminal Court* Vol. 35 155, Cornell International Law Journal

⁸ Article 38 of the Rome Statute, 1998

The Judicial Divisions consist of the 18 judges of the Court, organized into three chambers—the Pre-Trial Chamber, Trial Chamber and Appeals Chamber, which carry out the judicial functions of the Court. Judges are elected to the Court by the Assembly of States Parties. They serve nine-year terms and are not generally eligible for re-election. All judges must be nationals of the same state.⁹ They must be “persons of high moral character, impartiality and integrity who possess the qualifications required in their respective states for appointment to the highest judicial offices while observing the principle of national justice to its fullest.

The prosecutor or any person being investigated or prosecuted may request the disqualification of a judge from “any case in which his or her impartiality might reasonably be doubted on any ground.”¹⁰ Any request for the disqualification of a judge from a particular case is decided by an absolute majority of the other judges. The removal of a judge requires a two-third majority of the state parties.

c. **Office of the Prosecutor**

The office of the Prosecutor is responsible for conducting investigations and prosecution. It is headed by the Chief Prosecutor, who is assisted by one or more Deputy Prosecutors. The Rome Statute provides that the Office of the Prosecutor shall act independently, as such, no member of the Office may seek or act on instructions from any external source, such as states, international organizations or individuals.

The Prosecutor may open up an investigation under three circumstances:

- a) When a situation is referred to him or her by a state party,
- b) When a situation is referred to him or her by the United Nations Security Council, acting to address a threat to international peace and security; or
- c) When the Pre-Trial Chamber authorizes him or her to open an investigation on the basis of information received from other sources, such as individuals or non-governmental organizations.

Any person being investigated or prosecuted may request the disqualification of a prosecutor from any case “in which his impartiality might reasonably be doubted on any ground.”¹¹ Requests for the disqualification of prosecutors are decided by the Appeals Chamber.

Registry

The Registry is responsible for the non judicial aspects of the administration and servicing of the Court. This includes, “the administration of legal aid matters, court management, victims and witnesses matters, Defence counsel, detention unit, and the traditional services provided by administrations in international organizations, such as finance, translation, building management, procurement and personnel.” The Registry is headed by the Registrar, who is elected by the judges to a five-year term.

3. What is the trial procedure in ICC?

Trials are conducted under a hybrid common law and civil law judicial system, but it has been argued that the procedural orientation and character of the Court is still evolving. A majority of the three judges present at trial may reach a decision, which must include a full and reasoned statement. Trials are supposed to be public, but proceedings are often closed and such exceptions to a public trial have not been enumerated in detail. In camera proceedings are allowed, for protection of witnesses or defendants, as well as for confidential or sensitive evidence. Hearsay and other indirect evidence is not generally prohibited, but it has been argued that the Court is guided by hearsay exceptions which are prominent in common law systems. There is no subpoena or other means to compel witnesses to come before the Court, although the Court has some power to compel testimony of those who chose to come before it.

Does the Accused Have Rights in international criminal court (ICC)?

The Rome Statute provides that all persons are presumed innocent until proven guilty beyond reasonable doubt and establishes certain rights of the accused and persons during investigations.¹² These include the

⁹ Article 36 of the Rome Statute, 1998

¹⁰ Article 41 of the Rome Statute, 1998

¹¹ Article 42 of the Rome Statute, 1998

¹² The rights of persons during an investigation are provided in Article 55. Rights of the accused are provided in part 6, especially Article 67 of ICC Statute, 1998

right to be fully informed of the charges against him or her, the right to have a lawyer appointed, free of charge; the right to a speedy trial, and the right to examine the witnesses against him or her.

The ICC has established an independent Office of Public Counsel for the Defence (OPCD) to provide logistic support, advice and information to defendants and their counsel. The OPCD also helps to safeguard the rights of the accused during the initial stages of an investigation.

Participation of the Victim During Trial

Participation before the Court may occur at various stages of proceedings and may take different forms, although it is at the discretion of the judges to give directions as to the timing and manner of participation.

Participation in the Court's proceedings will in most cases take place through a legal representative and will be conducted "in a manner which is not prejudicial or inconsistent with the rights of the accused and a fair and impartial trial".

The victim based provisions within the Rome Statute provide victims with the opportunity to have their voices heard and to obtain, where appropriate, some form of reparation for their suffering. It is the aim of this attempted balance between retributive and restorative justice that will enable the ICC to not only bring criminals to justice but also help the victims obtain some form of justice.

Article 43 (6) established a Victims and Witnesses Unit to provide "protective measures and security arrangements, counseling and other appropriate assistance for witnesses, victims who appear before the Court, and others who are at risk on account of testimony given by such witnesses"¹³. While, Article 68 sets out procedures for the "Protection of the victims and witnesses and their participation in the proceedings". The Court has also established an Office of Public Counsel for Victims, to provide support and assistance to victims and their legal representatives. The ICC does not have its own witness protection programme but rather must rely on national programmes to keep witnesses safe.

Issues of Reparation in International Criminal Court (ICC)

Victims before the International Criminal Court can also claim reparations under Article 75 of the Rome Statute, reparations can only be claimed when a defendant is convicted and at the direction of the Court's judges. Reparations can include compensation, restitution and rehabilitation, but other forms of reparations may be appropriate for individual, collective or community victims. Again, Article 79 of the Rome Statute establishes a Trust Fund to provide assistance before a reparation order to victims in a situation or to support reparations to victims and their families if the convicted person has no money. So far the Court has ordered reparations against Thomas Lubanga of Democratic Republic of Congo.

5. The Principle of Complementarity in International Criminal Court (ICC).

The principle of complementarity which permeates the ICC Statute confers primacy on domestic courts over the ICC. In other words, the Court's jurisdiction is complementary to domestic courts, and it can exercise jurisdiction only when national criminal courts are not available or are unable to perform. National sovereignty concerns informed the introduction of the principle of complementarity in the operation of the ICC.¹⁴ Article 17 provides that the ICC will defer its jurisdiction to a national court except in situations where national courts have been genuinely unable or unwilling to investigate and/or prosecute the accused.¹⁵ Moreso, Article 17 is applicable even when the state's leaders are implicated.¹⁶ The prosecutor has the duty to notify all states that might exercise jurisdiction of his intention. The state, whether a state party or not may inform the Court that it is investigating the situation domestically.¹⁷ In

¹³ Article 43 (6) of the Rome Statute, 1998

¹⁴ Article 1 of ICC Statute, 1998 provides that the power to exercise its jurisdiction over persons concern as referred to in this Statute, and shall be complementary to national criminal jurisdiction.

¹⁵ ICC Statute, Article 17(a), 1998

¹⁶ ICC Statute, Article 28, 1998

¹⁷ ICC Statute, Article 18(2), 1998 provides that within one month of receipt of notification, a state may inform the Court that it is investigating or has investigated its nationals or others within its jurisdiction with respect to criminal acts which may constitute crimes referred to in Article 5 and which relate to the information provided in the notification to states. At the request of that

such an event, the prosecutor must defer to that investigation.¹⁸ The statute places the onus on the ICC prosecutor to prove that a state is unable or unwilling to prosecute or that investigations and trials carried out by a state are fraudulent.¹⁹ It has been suggested that a state may be unable to prosecute if it lacks the required manpower and institutions to carry out meaningful criminal prosecutions.²⁰ Such a situation could have arisen after the genocide in Rwanda, where very few lawyers and judges survived the 1994 massacre.²¹ A state may be unwilling to do so, if it lacks the political will. This may occur where the accused is a member of the state government or exerts influence over or accepts favours from those in government. With all due respect, this is common in Africa Continent.

A closer look of Article 17 was ostensibly drafted to accommodate and protect the United State interest. Under the complementarity provision, the United States may actually prevent the international criminal court (ICC) from exercising jurisdiction over its citizens by informing the court of its willingness to investigate the allegation under Article 18 (2).²² In the event that the pre-trial chamber rejects such request, Article 18 (4) allows the Appeal Chamber.²³ Under Article 18 (7) a state which has challenged a ruling of the pre-trial chamber may challenge the admissibility of the case under Article 19 on grounds of additional significant facts or change of circumstances. With these arrangements, the possibility that the United States or any state party to the Rome Statute would not maintain control over a case involving its citizen is exceedingly remote.²⁴

However with an advanced judicial system and history of criminal prosecution, it is difficult to imagine a situation where an investigation or prosecution carried out by the U.S. will be considered fraudulent. Therefore, the U.S. exercises jurisdiction over its nationals under the principle of complementarity²⁵ but the extent, African country can do this is still much unrealistic.

International Criminal Court and its trajectory of enforcement in Africa

African Union's resistance and failure to cooperate with the UN Security Council referral to ICC in case of Darfur, and Sudan, may be a good indication to the selectivity of enforcement of international criminal law in Africa by International Criminal Court . However, a firm conviction that impunity is no longer a shield for the atrocities and human rights violations in Africa, some African countries warmly welcomed the coming into existence of the ICC.

The pursuit of international criminal justice in Africa through the ICC platform has not been without hitches. There is a rift between the African Union (AU), as a continental body, and the ICC, owing to the AU's perception of the ICC as pursuing selective justice.²⁶ Some State parties in Africa have also refused or failed to comply with their obligations to cooperate with the ICC under the Rome Statute. The ICC's indictments have created tensions and aggravated conflicts and humanitarian situations in places such as Uganda and Sudan, as Darfur reported that the Lord's Resistance Army to the ICC's indictment of its leaders. Further, the Lord's Resistance Army (LRA) also investigated their attacks against the civilian population and aid workers as a reaction backed out of the peace process, claiming that a ceasefire would be misinterpreted by the ICC and government as occasioned by the indictments.

The ICC has been accused of being "part of a new mechanism of neo-colonialism", supporters of the ICC and in particular those in favour of the indictment of the Sudanese President maintained that the ICC's intervention is a right step towards the realization of human dignity, addressing impunity, facilitating

state, the prosecutor shall defer to the state's investigation of those persons unless the Trial Chamber, on the application of the prosecutor, decides to authorize the investigation.

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ ICC Statute 17 (2) (3), 1998

²⁰ David Rider, *Pans New International Court: "Arbour says Rules Shield World's Worst Criminals"*, *The Ottawa Citizen* at A7, 2002

²¹ Ibid.

²² ICC Statute Article 18 (2), 1998.

²³ ICC Statute Article 18 (4) , 1998.

²⁴ ICC Statute, Article 19 (2) (b), 1998

²⁵ ICC Statute, Article 20 (3), 1998.

²⁶ International Criminal Court (ICC), Outreach Report 2009 available at

<https://www.iccpi.int/NRrdonlyres/8A3D8107-5421-423AA64-D5 AB32D33271/or 2009 ENG Web pdf>.

democracy and peace, and for ensuring justice for the victims.²⁷ The ICC's interventions in Africa have had serious political, legal and social implications for the communities involved that should not be ignored. The ICC's indictments to date are only in connection with alleged offences regarding the conflict situations in Africa, namely Uganda, Central Africa Republic (CAR), Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Sudan, Republic of Kenya, Libya, Cote D'ivoire and Mali. The ICC came into these cases through referrals from governments and the UN Security Council and by the prosecutor's investigations. The cases are currently at different stages of investigation and trial, with only one concluded. The Rome Statute is very active and operative in Africa. It should be noted that Africa was the foremost in providing support for the ICC and that Senegal was the first country to ratify the ICC Statute.²⁸ Some African governments and individuals have cooperated with the ICC, while others such as Sudan; have refused to cooperate; Uganda cooperated, but was unable to comply with its treaty obligations to hand over indictees in their territory to the ICC. The AU has opposed the ICC's operations in African situations and has threatened to get its members to withdraw from the ICC and asked its member states not to cooperate with ICC.²⁹ There is an impasse between the AU and the ICC because the AU has accused the ICC of engaging in selective justice, in that the ICC indictments relating to only African situations and only Africans are being pursued so far.³⁰ The AU has raised concerns about the indictment/trial of sitting African heads of state. The implication of the impasse is that some of the indictees are at large and state parties have failed or refused to carry out the ICC's request to arrest them.

The ICC has been accused of bias and as being a tool of western imperialism, only punishing leaders from small, weak states, while ignoring crimes from rich and more powerful states. This sentiment has been expressed particularly by African leaders due to an alleged disproportionate focus of the Court on Africa, while it claims to have a global mandate; until January 2016, all nine situations which the ICC had been investigating were in African countries.

The prosecution of Kenyan Deputy President William Ruto and President Uhuru Kenyatta (both charged before coming into office) led to the Kenyan Parliament passing a motion calling for Kenya withdrawal from the ICC,³¹ and the country called on the other 33 African States party to the ICC to withdraw their support, an issue which was discussed at a special African Union (AU) summit in October 2013.³²

Though the ICC has denied the charge of disproportionately targeting African leaders, and claims to stand up for victims wherever they may be, Kenya was not alone in criticizing the ICC, former Sudanese President, Omar-al-Bashir visited Kenya, South Africa, China, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia ,United Arab Emirates ,Egypt, Ethiopia, Qatar and several other countries, despite an outstanding International criminal court warrant for his arrest, he was not arrested; he said that the charges against him are "exaggerated" and that the ICC was part of a "Western Plot" against him. Ivory Coast's government opted not to transfer first lady Simone Gbagbo to the Court, but opted to try her at home. Rwanda's former ambassador to the African Union, Joseph Nsegimana argued that "it is not only the case of Kenya, we have seen international justice become more and more a political matter". Ugandan President, Yoweri Museveni accused the ICC of "mishandling complex African issues"³³. Ethiopian Prime Minister Haile Mariam, at the time was AU Chairman, he told the UN General Assembly at the General debate of the sixty-eight session of the United Nations General Assembly that "the manner in which the ICC has been operating has left a very bad impression in Africa".

²⁷ A de Waal, "Sudan and the Controversy" available at

<http://opendemocracy.net/article/Sudan-and-theinternational-criminal-court-a-guide-to-the-controversy>

²⁸ C.C. Jalloh, "Regionalizing International Law Review, Vol. 9, 2009 pp 445-499

²⁹ D. Tladi: "The African Union and the International Criminal Court: The Battle for the Soul of International Law, Vol. 34, 2009, pp 57-69

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Global Policy Forum, International Criminal Court Investigations Kenya, available at www.globalpolicy.org/international-justice/theinternationalcriminal-court/icc-investigation/kenya.html

³² A.U, Extraordinary session of the Assembly of the African Union, 12 October, 2013, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, Decision on Africa's Relationship with the International Criminal Court (ICC), Ext./Assembly/AU/Dec. 1 (October 2013) Para. 1

³³ P. Apps "ICC Hopes for Uganda Trial in 6 Months then Congo" Reuters, available at www.globapolicy.org/int/justice/ice/2005/0126_ugandatrial.htm.

Former South African President Jacob Zuma said the perceptions of the ICC as “unreasonable” led to the calling of the special AU summit on 13 October, 2015. Botswana is a notable supporter of the ICC in Africa. At the summit, the AU did not endorse the proposal for a mass withdrawal from the ICC due to lack of support for the ideal. However, the summit did conclude that serving heads of state should not be put on trial and that the Kenyan cases should be deferred. Despite protests of some Africans, the ICC went ahead with requiring William Ruto to attend his trial. The United Nation Security Council was then asked to consider deferring the trial of Kenyatta and Ruto for a year, but this was rejected.³⁴

On the 7th October 2016 Burundi announced that it would leave the ICC after the court began investigating political violence in the nation. In the subsequent two weeks, South Africa and Gambia also announced their intention to leave the court with Kenya and Namibia reportedly considering departure. All three nations cited the fact that all 39 people indicted by the court over its history have been African and that Court has made no effort to investigate war crime tied to 2003 invasion of Iraq, while same as happen between Israel and Gaza this year 2025, and absolutely nothing has been done by ICC. However, following Gambia’s presidential election in later 2003, which ended the long rule of Yaya Jahmeh, Gambia rescinded its withdrawal notification. The High Court of South African ruled on 2 February 2017, the South African Government notice to withdraw was unconstitutional and invalid. On 7th March, the South African Government formally revoked its intention to withdraw. Again Africans are watching ICC over the June 2025 invasion of the Iran by Israel and America ,whether the government actors of these super powers will face international criminal charges for violating international laws is another issue for the ICC.

African cases before the ICC are either self-referral or UN Security Council referral. Self-referral made by African nations includes Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) against Thomas Lubanga and others, Central Africa Republic (CAR) against Jean-Piere Bemba Gombo, Uganda against Joseph Kony and Siera Leone against Charles Taylor.³⁵ Cote d'Ivoire without being a member consented and Kenya because of *prioro motu*.

The claim that ICC is targeting Africans while ignoring similar cases elsewhere is not tenable, African states actively participated in the making of the Rome Statute, and ICC assume jurisdiction of African cases because the nations referred the cases to the ICC with exception to the cases of Darfur, Sudan, against Al Bashir and Libya which were referred by United Nation Security Council.

In all, ICC cannot be blamed for selective justice once the UNSC is sustaining the referred procedure, there should be no confusion between ICC and UNSC as both are different and independent organs with different objectives. A referral is a mechanism of investigation by the ICC Prosecutors whether there are reasonable grounds to commence prosecution against those crimes the ICC has jurisdiction over, the ICC may exercise jurisdiction if a situation in which one or more of such crimes appear to have been committed is referred to the Prosecutor by a state party in accordance with Article 14 of the statute.³⁶ The ICC may exercise jurisdiction upon a referral made by states *proprio motu* as articulated under Articles 13(c) cum 15.³⁷ The UN Security Council referral mandate under Chapter VII of the UN Charter which permits it to take non-member countries to the ICC is a violation of the Vienna Convention on the Laws of Treaties³⁸

The ICC is neither an organ to the UN nor subsidiary to the Security Council, but it is an independent organ having jurisdiction over cases of genocide, crimes, humanity, war crimes and aggression. However, the existence of relationship to the UN Security Council appears inexorable due to Article 2 of the ICC through a certain agreement. This relationship in its face appears simple but it has legal and political connotations embodied inside it. This relationship brings three ways into play: in a complementary fashion, where the Council and Court act in harmony; in a conflictual manner, where they take opposing

³⁴ Security Council SC/11176, 15 November 2013, available at www.un.org/News/Press/docs/2013/SC11176.doc.htm

³⁵ Marlise Simons & J. David Goodman, “Ex-Liberian Leader Gets 50 Years for War Crimes”, N.Y. Times, 31 May 2012

³⁶ ICC Statute Article 14, 1998

³⁷ ICC Statute Article 13, 1998

³⁸ Chapter VII of the UN Charter, 1945

positions or try to usurp the competence of each other; or in an overlapping way, where they pursue their own agenda without regard to the other, even though they may be dealing with the situation.

The UN Security Council may refer a case for investigation to the ICC in exercising its mandate³⁹ under Chapter VII of Restoration of International Peace and Security. Conversely, Article 16 of the ICC Statute allowed the Council to block the jurisdiction of the Court, thus giving the Council certain supremacy, but again only if it were able to garner the necessary votes in the Council and avoid veto from a permanent member. Controversies could increase between the two organs because some countries are members to the UN Charter but not the ICC and vice versa which highlights differential interests involving both organizations. Therefore, the UN Security Council could be used as a shielding mechanism by the super power like the United State. This is already playing out in the war between Israel, America and Iran in June 2025. This is because of the existence of Article 103 of the UN Charter giving prevalence over other treaties.⁴⁰ Article 13 (b) was seen as an opportunity for the Security Council, because the Article enables the council to refer the case to already established judicial body like the ICC without the need to establish ad hoc tribunals. However, the addition of Article 16 is not producing the required result, because it is a power given to the UN Security Council to limit the power of the ICC to adjudicate by deferring which reads as follows:

*No investigation or prosecution may be commenced or proceeded
Or with under this statute for a period of 12 months after the Security
Council, in a Resolution adopted under Chapter VII of the Charter of
the United Nations, has requested the Court to that effect; that request
may be renewed by the Council under the same conditions.*⁴¹

In many instances both the UN Security Council and the ICC are different organizations, though they have some points of convergence. The UN Security Council is a political organ, and it is striving for international peace and security, whereas the ICC works for rendition of justice. Incontrovertibly, ICC is a purely legal institution, rather than a political body.⁴²

The issue of whether the crimes for which ICC has intervened in African situation are indeed covered by Rome Statute needs to be well considered. The ICC has always asserted it has intervened in the situations because crimes within its jurisdiction have been committed in those places. It needs to be questioned whether the governments with the primary responsibility to hold perpetrators accountable for such crimes are unwilling or unable to do so and thereby warrant ICC's intervention.

The issue of selective judgment against African countries must be considered against the perspective of whether events that triggered ICC's intervention in African situations have occurred elsewhere around the globe and the ICC ignored it or is ignoring such countries while picking only on Africa. It has been argued that similar situations that ICC is pursuing have occurred or are occurring in Afghanistan, Gaza or Palestine, and Iran but have been overlooked and Africa has become the ICC's "laboratory".⁴³

The allegation of selective justice is also considered under the circumstances that would undermine the very essence of global justice. The ICC Statute could apply to any situation, because even if the state is not a party to the Rome Statute, the Security Council could refer a situation in a non-state party to the ICC and the ICC would exercise jurisdiction over such a matter. The argument is that though no state is immune from the ICC's jurisdiction, critics have argued that it applies only to weaker states and not powerful states, this is because major powers have become players and referees, formulating the rules of the game but refusing to play by them. The main reason is that out of the five permanent members of the UN Security Council, three, namely US, China and Russia are not members of the ICC Statute. The US,

³⁹ Ibid

⁴⁰ Article 103 of the UN Charter, 1945

⁴¹ Ibid

⁴² Article 24:1 of the UN Charter, 1945

⁴³ T. McNamme, 'The ICC and Africa Between Aspirations and Reality Making: International Justice Work Better for Africa, Reflections on a High-Level Roundtable 18-19 March, 2014 Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, Co hosted by the Brenthrust Foundation and The African Center for Strategic Studies Brethrust Discussion Paper 2, 2014

apart from not being a state party to the ICC, has also entered into an agreement with other states not to surrender American citizens to the ICC, but to hand them over to treaty obligations to America because the ICC is enjoined not to make requests from states if compliance by such states with the ICC's request would jeopardize the state's treaty obligations to other states.⁴⁴ The stands adopted by China, United States and Russia on the ICC undermine the very essence of the global criminal justice idea enshrined in the ICC Statute and send negative signals to Africa and the rest of the world that they and their affiliates are immuned from the ICC. Can any African countries enjoy this privilege as independent nation in their various territorial sovereignty? A big question yet to be answered.

7. CONCLUSION

The International Criminal Court should not be described as an organization that chases Africans and African Leaders, but it deals with hard situations to protect future occurrences of abuses in Africa and other parts of the world. It is worthy to state here that the International criminal court recently convicted two anti-balaka militia leaders for serious crimes in the Central African Republic. On July 24, 2025, ICC judges convicted Alfred Yekatom on charges involving 20 war crimes and crimes against humanity and Patrice-Edward Ngaissona on charges involving 28 war crimes and crimes against humanity committed in the Central African Republic between December 2013 and August 2014. The judges sentences Yekatom to 15 years in prison and Ngaissana to 12 years.⁴⁵ It becomes political, however when the alleged perpetrator happens to be the government, as in the case of Sudan⁴⁶ and Kenya⁴⁷. It is imperative that African governments live up to their obligations to the ICC and take genuine steps to stop and prevent impunity on their shores within the law. The desirability of ICC's intervention in the African situation does not rule out the allegation of selective justice when the ICC overlooks similar situation elsewhere in the globe such as the activities of Isreal against Gaza in the ongoing war.

The ICC's intervention in African situations is justifiable, since the situations involve commission of alleged crimes within the ICC's jurisdiction. However, there can be an assertion of selective justice if countries are allowed to work their way out of the jurisdiction of the ICC as have the United States and other permanent members of the Security Council. Also, an assessment of the global population of state and non state parties reflect some form of selective justice. The state parties of the ICC make up 30% of the world population while 70% make up the population of non state parties, so the majority are outside the jurisdiction of the ICC:

Be that as it may, there is a compelling need for the ICC to intensify its campaigns to bring the current non state parties to the Court.⁴⁸ The prevailing international position in dealing with war crimes and other breaches of human rights is to prosecute and punish the perpetrators. The ICC has a key responsibility to ensure that in its complementary capacity, it assists states. Though several African Countries supported the ICC initiative, it is clear that the ICC's intervention in Africa has created an impasse between the ICC and some governments in Africa and the AU as a continental body.

To this end, the charges against Al Bashir have only fuelled the view that the ICC is a neo-colonial project in which Westerners prosecute Africans⁴⁹. A non-African investigation and prosecution of cases would certainly help the Court to appear global in its reach. The ICC can only prosecute crimes

⁴⁴ Art 98 (1) Rome Statute, 1998

⁴⁵ <https://www.hrw.org/news/2025/07/24/central-african-republic-icc-convicts-two-anti-balaka-leaders>

⁴⁶ K.G. Adar, "The International Criminal Court and the Indictment of President Omar Al-Bashir: Implications of Sudan and Africa, AISA Policy Brief, No 10, February 2010

⁴⁷ "Kenya: Impact of the ICC Proceedings, Africa Briefing.. No, 84, 9 Jan 2012, available at

www.crisgroup.org/en/regions/africa/horn-of-africa/kenya/b084-kenya-impact-of-the-icc-proceedings.aspx

⁴⁸ J.M. Mbaku, Africa's case against the ICC. Paper for panel discussion on "The International Criminal Court in Africa: Bias, Legitimate Objections, or Excuses for Impunity" Co-hosted by New York University's School for Continuing and Professional Studies (SCPS), Center for Global Affairs and the International Center for Transitional Justice (ICTJ). available at

www.edu/blogs/africa-in-focus/posts/2014/03/13--international-criminal-court-mbaku

⁴⁹ A de Waal, "Darfur, the Court and Khartoum: *The Politics of State Non-Cooperation*, in Waddel and Clark (eds), p 29-35

committed after the Rome Statute came into force in July 2002, so its early cases are either ongoing conflict situations or recently ceased conflicts.

The ICC has been able to remedy some of the deficiencies of the ad hoc tribunals, structurally, the court is a significant improvement because of its permanence, no longer international justice at the mercy of UNSC. The court has under strict conditions jurisdiction over any atrocity committed anywhere in the world. Operationally, the Court is expected to be more accessible, cheaper and more efficient than the Tribunals.

However the principle of complementary is regarded as one of the limitation of the ICC. This principle says a case will not be admissible, it is being investigated or prosecuted by a state which has jurisdiction unless the state is unwilling or unable to prosecute the offenders. By the provision, the system gives national court the opportunity to prosecute locally, the question of “unwilling or unable” has so far remained controversial.

Therefore, the efforts of the International Criminal Court to enforce the violations of humanitarian laws and establish international criminal justice in Africa has been with great hitches. The African Union has expressed some misgivings about the trial of some sitting heads of states in Africa. The accusation of ICC of selective justice undermines the regime of international criminal justice. Some of the challenges faced by the ICC arise from its failure to pay attention to the domestic contexts in order to harmonize its operations. The ICC's interventions in Africa have had serious political, legal and social implications for the communities involved, jeopardizing the peace equilibrium. For the ICC to prevent or prosecute international crimes in Africa would require a concerted effort by all concerned to harmonize the demand for justice with the imperatives on the ground. The ICC is still evolving as an institution and it is the first of its kind building upon the history of Nuremberg, Tokyo tribunals, the International Criminal Tribunal of Yugoslavia (ICTY) and the International Criminal Tribunal of Rwanda (ICTR). Though it has attracted numerous criticisms, the ICC has been dealing with complex international criminal law issues in a way that was never contemplated years ago. The ICC trials may not be devoid of notable challenges particularly as they apply to Africa, the ICC is an institution that is slowly but surely showing that it can work with national and regional courts to prosecute the violators of war crimes, crime against humanity and genocide.

In the words of Archbishop Desmond Tutu, a consummate cleric and hero of anti-apartheid struggle stated

“that when thousands of people are murdered and displaced in any country, one would hope that the country's own system of justice would move in to right the wrongs. He reasons that leaving ICC “would be a tragedy for Africa” for three reasons Firstly, without justice, countries can attack their neighbours or minorities in their own countries with impunity. Secondly, without justice, there can be no peace; and thirdly, as Africa finds its voice in world affairs, it should be strengthening justice and the rule of law, not undermining them”⁵⁰”

Archbishop Desmond Tutu opined that African leaders behind the move to extract the continent from the jurisdiction of the Court, were effectively seeking a license to kill, maim and oppress their people without consequences, and they are saying that the interests of the people should not be allowed to get in the way of their personal ambitions. Being held to account, according to him, interferes with their ability to act with impunity to achieve their objectives, and those who get in their way, that is their victims, should remain faceless and voiceless.⁵¹

⁵⁰ Tutu Desmond “Why Africa should not leave ICC” Punch Newspaper, 11 October, 2013

⁵¹ Ibid

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